

¿Harry Potter en Educación Deportiva? Percepciones del profesor, estudiantes y familias

Harry Potter in Sport Education? Teacher, students and parents' views

Abstract

The goal of this study was to examine teacher, students and parents' perceptions of a quidditch-muggle Sport Education season at a primary school. Fifty-two sixth-grade students from one primary school participated in the study. A case study research design was followed. One Physical Education specialist with expertise in the Sport Education Model agreed to participate and conducted a season based on the quidditch-muggle sport (17 sessions; 60 minutes/each, two days/week). Finally, forty-five parents, 86.52% of the total sample, agreed to provide their insights on their children's Harry Potter experience. Several instruments were used to collect qualitative data: teacher's diary, students' open-ended question, parents' open-ended question and students' discussion groups. From the analysis of all data obtained, four positive categories emerged: *enjoyment*, *novelty*, *learning and self-construction* and one negative: *competitiveness*. Teacher, students and parents highlighted the usefulness of the SEM despite of the overemphasis on the competition.

Keywords: pedagogical models; primary education; invasion games; physical education.

Resumen

El objetivo de este estudio fue examinar las percepciones del profesor, estudiantes y familias de una temporada de Educación Deportiva de quidditch-muggle. 52 estudiantes de 6º de Educación Primaria de un colegio participaron en la investigación. Se llevó a cabo un estudio de caso. Un profesor de Educación Física experto en el modelo de Educación Deportiva participó en el estudio y dirigió la temporada de quidditch-muggle (17 sesiones; 60 minutos por sesión, dos días a la semana). Finalmente, 45 familias, esto es un 86,52% del total de la muestra, aceptaron participar y proporcionar sus puntos de vista acerca de la experiencia de Harry Potter de sus hijos. Se utilizaron diferentes instrumentos de recogida de datos: diario del profesor, preguntas abiertas del alumnado, preguntas abierta de las familias y grupos de discusión del alumnado. Del análisis de datos se extrajeron cuatro categorías positivas: *diversión*, *novedad*, *aprendizaje y autoconstrucción* y una negativa: *competitividad*. El profesor, el alumnado y las familias destacaron la utilidad del modelo a pesar de la competitividad presente.

Keywords: modelos pedagógicos, educación primaria, juegos de invasion, educación física.

Introduction

Pedagogical models have emerged as one of the leading frameworks in today's Physical Education (PE) (Haerens et al., 2011). Basically, they all are based on the connections between learning, teaching, content and context (Rovegno, 2006). Pedagogical models have been found to produce positive outcomes in students and teachers (Casey, 2014), like Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility (Hellison, 2001), Cooperative Learning (Johnson et al., 2013), the Sport Education Model (SEM; Siedentop et al., 2019) or Teaching Games for Understanding (Bunker & Thorpe, 1982) to name some of them. The use of these models and/or its combinations on a regular basis has been called Models-based Practice (Casey, 2016), and it has become very popular in many schools worldwide.

The SEM (Siedentop et al., 2019) is probably the most popularly implemented/researched pedagogical model internationally, since its appearance in the mid 90s with the publication of the first Sport Education book (Siedentop et al., 2019). Throughout the 1980s, Siedentop found that PE classes were based on a wide variety of contents taught in short learning units. Students focused on the performance of technical-tactical skills in isolated tasks (analytic context) in the first steps of the learning unit and later, they were asked to put into practice those skills in a real situation (global context). Although some students were able to achieve the set standards, the level of implication and enthusiasm was rather low (Calderón et al., 2011). Moreover, the learning units were not adequate in terms of learning, as most students were not able to translate the skills learned to the real game. With this in mind, Siedentop tried to create a model that could involve students in a long-term experience to achieve the goal of the SEM: to create competent, enthusiastic and literate students (Siedentop et al., 2019). To reach this goal, the SEM was structured around six basic elements: (1) *Seasons*: instructional interventions are organized into "seasons", which are longer than traditional learning units; (2) *Affiliation*: students are organized into small, heterogeneous teams that remain together during the whole season. In addition, teams create a cheer, flags, banners, t-shirts, etc. to foster attachment. (3) *Formal competition*: throughout the entire season, teams compete against each other following different formats: dual meets, round robin, progressive competition season, events, etc. (4) *Culminating event*: the season ends with the tournament finals and a celebration where awards are given to both students and teams. (5) *Record keeping*: during the learning unit, points and scores are awarded to provide both individual and team feedback: duty-team performance, fair-play points, games results, etc. (6) *Festivity*: the whole learning unit is surrounded by a festive atmosphere to foster excitement and motivation. Finally, *students' roles* (i.e., referee, coach, captain, etc.) are also fundamental in the SEM, because they can

increase, among other, students' involvement and responsibility. An overview of the research conducted on the SEM over the last 30 years has been synthesized in several systematic reviews, which highlighted the positive outcomes, as well as some weaknesses (Bessa et al., 2019; Evangelio et al., 2018; Hastie et al., 2011; Hastie & Wallhead, 2016; Wallhead & O'Sullivan, 2007).

Traditional sports like basketball, soccer or volleyball have been the dominant force in PE for many years (Cohen & Peachey, 2015; Gray, Sproule, & Morgan, 2009), and in many places, they still are. Many research projects have used these sports as the main content in SEM learning units (Farias, Harvey, Hastie, & Mesquita, 2019; Farias, Mesquita, & Hastie, 2019; Farias, Valério and Mesquita, 2018; Kao, 2019; Rocamora, González-Víllora, Fernández-Río and Arias-Palencia, 2019). Fortunately, non-traditional sports, "activities that either ideologically or practically provide alternatives to mainstream sports and mainstream sport values" (Rinehart, 2000, p. 506), are slowly finding their place in today's PE. The benefits from their practice include no masculine hegemony, no high or low skilled students (they all start from "scratch") or novelty (it can promote students' motivation; Cohen, Melton & Peachey, 2014).

Several non-traditional sports/contents have been implemented using the SEM and some of them have assessed the participants' perceptions. Fernández-Río and Menéndez (2017) analysed teacher and students' perceptions of a hybrid SEM and Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility learning unit using educational kickboxing and found that the hybrid model helped increase students' personal and social responsibility and healthy competitiveness. In addition, kickboxing was seen as a novel sport that fostered students' motivation in PE classes. For their part, Fittipaldi-Wert et al. (2009) studied the effects of a SEM learning unit on students with visual impairments using sports like boccia or goalball and found that the experience helped provide authentic sporting experiences. Being part of a team, the festivity and the sports played during the camp were positive aspects that the students valued. Chong and Penney (2013) analysed students' abilities to handle failure in PE in elementary school in an ultimate-frisbee SEM learning unit and found that both the sport and the model helped pupils increase their emotional learning to cope with failure. Martínez et al., (2016) studied the long-term effects of three non-traditional sports (pichi, indicas and ultimate-frisbee) using the SEM and found that they were useful to increase students' sense of game, motivation, cooperation and social responsibility. Finally, not only individual or collective sports have been introduced using the SEM. Mendez-Gimenez et al., analysed students' perceptions of a SEM learning unit of mime and found that it helped increase students' emotional

intelligence and peer relationships. Other non-traditional sports/activities have been implemented using the SEM: table-tennis (Buchanan & Barrow, 2016), obstacle course (Hastie et al., 2009), cross-fit or even fishing (Wahl-Alexander et al., 2018). All the abovementioned studies indicate that the SEM framework can be adapted to teach almost any content and that novelty could be a key principle to increase students' motivation and adherence to PE.

One of the reasons that lead teachers to introduce new contents in their school's curriculum is the search for novelty. One of the most important theoretical frameworks used to understand human behaviour in different settings (i.e., education, sport, healthcare) is the Self-Determination Theory (SDT; Ryan & Deci, 2002). This theory tries to define the grade in which people act with the maximum degree of voluntariness and reflection (Deci & Ryan, 1985) and the type of motivation that guides individuals (intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation or amotivation). The SDT comprises six mini-theories, among them the Basic Psychological Needs Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2017), which identifies three: competence, autonomy and relatedness, that individuals must satisfy to feel emotionally safe. In recent years, novelty, defined as the drive "to commit to interesting activities" (Gonzalez-Cutre et al., 2016, p. 160) has been added to this short list of basic psychological needs. Recent research has linked the need for novelty to liveliness, dispositional flow, and satisfaction in Physical Education (Gonzalez-Cutre & Sicilia, 2019), which for many may seem unnecessary, but research tells us that some students feel amotivated in these classes (Ntoumanis, 2001) and that a change is needed.

In the search for novelty, non-traditional sports can play a role, and one of them is quidditch, from J. K. Rowling's fictional Harry Potter story (Rowling, 1997). This game has been adapted to real life, creating a new version called quidditch-muggle (Muggles are non-magical people in Harry Potter's films). It combines elements from dodgeball (throwing balls at other players) and rugby-tag (stealing flags from opposite players) and other sports (Cohen & Peachey, 2015). Very little research has been conducted on Quidditch-Muggle, and all of it has been conducted in extracurricular contexts (Cohen et al., 2012; Cohen et al., 2014). Moreover, there are no published studies that have examined the implementation of this sport using the SEM. Therefore, there seems to be a need to continue filling the gap regarding the possibilities of the SEM framework to be adapted to new sports, and provide reliable data for researchers and educators.

Based on the aforementioned, the goal of this study was to examine teacher, students and parents' perceptions of a quidditch-muggle SEM learning unit in Primary Education. The present study brought three research questions: a) is "content novelty" enough to produce

positive outcomes? b) has there been an impact “at home”? and c) is “competitiveness” an issue in the SEM?

Method

Participants

Fifty-two sixth-grade students, 11-13 years (mean age 11.3), from one Primary School located in Northern Spain participated in the study. They were enrolled in three different classes: A: 18 students (10 males, 8 females), B: 18 students (9 males, 9 females) and C: 16 students (8 males, 8 females). Students’ socioeconomic background could be considered medium. All of them followed the same Physical Education (PE) programme: two weekly sessions of 60 minutes. None of the participants had previously experienced either Sport Education or Quidditch-Muggle. One specialist PE teacher conducted the same learning unit in all the classes. He can be considered an expert on the SEM, since he earned his PhD researching it. He has conducted several SEM seasons in Primary and Secondary Education throughout his teaching career. Moreover, at the time of the study, he was also working as an assistant professor on initial teacher training. Finally, all fifty-two parents were also invited to participate in the study, and a significant 86.52% (forty-five parents) agreed (age range 34-58 years) to provide their insights on their children’s Harry Potter experience. The only inclusion criteria to be part of the research was to be a sixth-grade student of the school and a mother/parent of the students.

Desing and procedure

A case study research desing was followed (Montero & Leon, 2007). Firstly, it was obtained permission from the Ethical Committe of the researchers’ university. Secondly, the school’s headmaster and the head of studies were informed about the Quidditch project, since some sessions took place at the playground during recess with the other school students around, and one of the school’s sport facilities was used. Both granted permission to conduct the study. Thirdly, the intervention program was fully explained to the participating students and to their families, and a written informed consent was obtained from all of them.

Intervention program

Following Hastie and Casey (2014, p. 423) fidelity of the implementation should be supported through: “(a) a rich description of the curricular elements of the unit, (b) a detailed validation of model implementation and (c) a detailed description of the program context”. Regarding the detailed program context, all participating classes experienced the same intervention program: the Quidditch-Muggle game, the sport from the Harry Potter story, which was adapted to fit the participating school’s needs. Two teams of five players competed

against each other. The basic goal was to introduce a ball inside one of the three hoops located at different heights on each side of the playing field. Obviously, students run instead of fly, and used foam pool noodles instead of wooden brooms. There were three types of players: one keeper, three chasers and one seeker-beater. There were also three types of balls: one quaffle (a medium size foam ball), two bludgers (small foam balls) and one golden snitch (a floorball ball). Chasers tried to introduce the quaffle into one of the three hoops, while the keeper tried to avoid it using a short racquet. Finally, due to the number of students per class, one player was at the same time seeker and beater: he/she had to use the bludger to hit the opposite team's chasers, maintaining a 2-3 meters distance to avoid hard hits. When one chaser was hit, he/she had to go to the "resurrection area" located in the corner of the playing field, touch the cone that was there and come back to the game. The seeker-beater also had to try to catch the golden snitch. The teacher gave this ball to a student of the team that was not playing, put a flag in the student's pants and he/she entered the playing field to run around. The seekers-beaters tried to catch the flag and obtain the golden snitch. Scores were as follows: 30 points for the middle hoop, 20 points for the other hoops and 40 points for the golden snitch.

Regarding the rich description of the learning unit (Table 1), it was designed following the SEM framework (Siedentop et al., 2019).

Table 1

Quidditch-Muggle unit plan.

Session	Activities
1	Introduction to the SEM (country selection, daily roles, team cheer, etc..) and to the Quidditch-Muggle game (players, balls, rules, etc.).
2-4	Basic Quidditch-Muggle skills (move with the foam pool noodles, passes, throws, catching actions, etc.) and friendly matches.
5	Countries' parade.
6-9	Formal competition: tournament first "leg", practice.
10-13	Formal competition: tournament second "leg", practice.
14-16	Championship finals (during recess periods).
17	Awards ceremony.

The season lasted 17 sessions and it was divided in three different parts: pre-season (basic Quidditch-Muggle skills learning) season (formal competition) and the culminating event (finals) and the awards ceremony. It was an inter-classes league where the nine teams of

sixth-grade (three per class) participated. Students performed different roles that rotated on a daily basis: conditioning coach, equipment manager, referee and speaker. The conditioning coach led the group’s warm up on each session using one designed by the group itself. The equipment manager was in charge of the team equipment and helped the teacher at the beginning and at the end of the session to assemble the game. The referee was in charge of upholding rules during gameplay and finally the speaker, whose main function was to comment on the game during the finals. Following Luguetti et al. (2017), table 2 describes the key features of the SEM and how they were implemented throughout the learning unit.

Table 2

Key features of Sport Sducation in the learning unit.

Key features	In the learning unit
Season	It was divided in three parts: pre-season (sessions 1 to 4), season (session 5 to 13) and the culminating event which included the finals and the awards ceremony.
Affiliation	From the beginning, students were grouped in heterogeneous teams (skills, gender, ethnic background), where they remained during the whole unit.
Formal competition	The teams played in two round-robin tournaments where training and matches were combined. All teams (3 teams per class) participated in the league.
Culminating event	Three days of finals were scheduled at the school’s playground during recess, where each team competed against one of the two other classes. At the end of the season, an awards ceremony was celebrated to recognize both individual and team achievements
Record keeping	Points were awarded and recorded in the championship’s competition board for different tasks: role performance, hygiene (bring a clean t-shirt to wear after class), fair play and games’ scores.
Festivity	Teams had to represent a country, design flags and self-constructed t-shirts, and create a “cheer”. Students were asked to bring a self-constructed medal and a trophy per team to exchange during the awards ceremony.

Data collection

Several instruments were used to collect qualitative data and try to to obtain a holistic view of the experience:

Teacher's diary. Following Chen, Sinelnikov, and Hastie's (2013) recommendations, a teacher's diary was used to help the participating teacher focus on "critical incidents" of the experience. At the end of each lesson, the teacher answered two questions: (1) What was the most important or meaningful issue that took place? (2) Why was it important or meaningful?

Students' open-ended question. At the end of the intervention program, all the participants answered the following question: "Describe your feelings, thoughts and ideas on the Quidditch-Muggle learning unit that you just experienced in Physical Education". They were asked to fully explain their ideas using one sheet of paper, but not to mention issues that the teacher knew in advance (e.g., rules, types of players, etc.).

Parents' open-ended question. At the end of the intervention, all students' parents received a letter with the following open-ended question: "Please, tell us what did your son/daughter tell you about the Quidditch-Muggle experience? Do not include things that the teacher already knows (i.e., rules, types of players...), but tell us anecdotes or significant events".

Students' discussion groups. Three discussion groups (one per class) of five students from different teams were conducted at the end of the intervention program. Each one lasted 20-30 minutes. The researcher asked the students about the teaching approach (i.e., roles, session design, etc.), the global perception of the learning unit, teamwork... They were all recorded with a Zoom H5 recorder. Student selection criteria were three: a) willingness to participate, b) at least one player from each team; and c) speaking fluency (to obtain enough information). Discussion groups were used instead of individual interviews for time reasons (there was not enough time to conduct interviews).

Researchers guaranteed participants that all the responses obtained through the different instruments were going to be treated anonymously, and that they would not affect the students' Physical Education marks.

Data analysis

All information: discussion groups, teacher's diary and students' and parents' open-ended questions were transcribed verbatim by the main author of the research, producing 45 single-spaced, Times New Roman 12, pages of data. After transcribe all data, the main author read again all pages to detect mistakes and erratumas, modifying only minor issues that had no effect in the global sense of each extract. After this, and in order to assist with qualitative data management, Atlas.ti 7.5 was used to organise all data. All participants' answers were analysed using thematic content analysis (Libarkin & Kurdziel, 2002) and constant comparison (Denzin & Lincoln, 1994) whereby all data were organised into positive or negative categories,

producing five different categories (four positive and one negative). As regards categories, first, both researchers analysed all data separately, to determine initial categories independently. Those categories emerged naturally from data after reading several times the participants' extracts. Then, all categories were examined and compared by both researchers at the same time in order to detect misinterpretations and/or discrepancies (Miles et al., 2013). Finally, both researchers reached an agreement to determine the final categories/themes. In the results section, positive categories were ordered taking into consideration its recurrence in the analysis. Thus, enjoyment category was the most recurrent in all data, reason why it was placed firstly and so on.

Results

Analysis of all data obtained from the teacher's diary, parents' and students' open-ended questions and discussion groups produced five categories/themes; four positive: *enjoyment, novelty, learning* and *self-construction* and one negative: *competitiveness*.

Each one is presented below with the number of meaningful segments and participants' extracts are used to illustrate. The following coding was used: teacher's diary (TD), parents' open-ended questions (POEQ), students' open-ended questions (SOEQ), and discussion groups (DG).

Enjoyment. Many students reflected how important and funny had been the experience: "This is an activity to enjoy. Laughs, hugs, claps, shouts, celebrations... The best moments of your childhood, those that you spend with your friends are forged thanks to activities like this" (Juan, SOEQ). Many comments reflected the excitement during the finals, which could be considered remarkable, because they were held during recess, the only break that students have at school: "when it was raining and we couldn't play the finals it was... please stop. I really wanted to play" (Laura, SOEQ). The teacher also annotated some comments:

"The mannequins that students painted on the school's walls included the colours and flags of the teams that they represented in the Quidditch-Muggle championship. They reflect students' interest, involvement and enjoyment in the activity" (TD, sesión 6).

Other comments were related to the atmosphere created during the intervention program: "I found the activity very entertaining as it was like being in the Harry Potter's films" (Sara, DG). Many reported that the Quidditch league created was fun: "I liked the idea of a league between classes, because it was like a sport tournament, which is fun...I had friends in other classes and I enjoyed playing against them during recess" (Sara, SOEQ). Parents also reflected on the positive aspects of the championship: "The fact that all classes participated involved many participants to make it more enjoyable" (Sandra, POEQ). They also reflected

the interest that the Quidditch-Muggle experience had produced in the children: “Our daughter was really excited with this experience, especially during lunch. She didn’t stop talking about the championship” (Naiara, POEQ).

Likewise, the structure of the season was positively commented: “the pre-season was a fantastic idea, because it gave the teams time enough to adapt to the game and to be better as a team” (Luis, DG). The duration, longer than traditional learning units, was also a positive element: “Twelve sessions have passed and I don’t see the students bored. On the contrary, they are highly motivated” (TD, session 12). The point system (*record keeping*) was another positive issue that fostered enjoyment: “it was a good idea... the points for fair play, for bringing the clean t-shirt... I think the points made us a bit more interested in doing things better” (Sandra, SOEQ). Likewise, other elements of the SEM like the festive atmosphere were positively commented by the students:

“Today, we had the countries’ parade and it was a fascinating session in all senses. Students had to go to class with the affiliation items and the self-constructed flags and it was incredible: painted t-shirts and incredible flags... really big and spectacular. It reflects students’ involvement” (TD, session five).

The awards ceremony was another especial moment that many students commented: “the awards ceremony was really exciting, because we didn’t know in what position we were going to end” (Rebeca, SOEQ). Finally, roles like conditioning coach or speaker were also highlighted, and the students thought that there were educative and fun. However, the most recurrent role in students’ comments was the referee, a role of much responsibility:

“It’s a sport that I enjoyed a lot but not as much as I’d have liked, because I was injured during most of the trimester. Fortunately, I wasn’t bored because I was a referee and although sometimes I didn’t like it because people argued and mocked at me, I found the role fun” (Luis, SOEQ).

Novelty. This category includes all comments related to the Quidditch-Muggle sport. Some students highlighted how positive was to practice a new sport: “I found this activity really interesting because although I knew this sport from Harry Potter’s films, I never thought that it could be practiced as a real sport” (Carlos, SOEQ). “For me, play Quidditch was really cool because it was like being in Harry Potter’s films and books. It was fascinating” (Andre, SOEQ). The students valued the similarity with the game in the films: “I liked that the game in PE was very similar to the movies... with brooms, hoops, the snitch and so on” (Carlos, DG). The teacher also mentioned the importance of novelty in the PE classes: “They [students] felt highly motivated by the content itself, really new because they had never played it” (TD, session

three). He also reflected that the Quidditch experience was embedded into the students' school life: "I went to a class to pick up the pupils and they were playing with wand toys like they were in Harry Potter films" (TD, session six). Moreover, playing this new sport during recess, in front of other pupils, was also positive: "Little students watching a new sport... it was fantastic. They asked me what sport we were playing" (Sara, DG). Parents also highlighted the importance of novelty for their children: "Overall, he [son] liked the experience so much because it is different than what they usually do in PE" (Xana, POEQ). Other parents showed that the experience helped their children increase their interest in Harry Potter: "My son Marco is a great reader but he had never felt anything special about Harry Potter until he began to practice Quidditch in PE" (Carla, POEQ). Parents also highlighted how this learning unit had increased students' motivation to read: "Laura enjoyed this activity so much that she read the books, saw the films and now she loves Harry Potter" (Alberto, POEQ). Students commented on the roles experienced: "I loved being a hunter because I like throwing balls so much" (María, SOEQ) and the teacher: "Students loved being the golden snitch and run from the seeker. When I put the handkerchief to select the snitch [a student] they all come to me saying "I wanna be, I wanna be!" (TD, session five). Some students reported that they preferred to be the snitch rather than the seeker: "I loved being a guardian but I did not like trying to catch the snitch because it was really difficult" (Juan, SOEQ). Unfortunately, some students commented negatively on the foam pool noodles: "Carrying a foam pool noodle between your legs is a bit annoying because you couldn't run well and it fell off in the middle of the game" (Miguel, SOEQ).

Learning. Undoubtedly, the most recurrent learning outcome mentioned was *teamwork*. Many students commented that they had learned how to cooperate: "Quidditch-Muggle is a sport that helped me to cooperate with people I had never worked with" (Miguel, SOEQ). Parents also highlighted this theme: "The game has improved the team spirit: we have witnessed how this experience has promoted communication, coordination and collaboration among students" (Sandra, POEQ). For its part, *motor learning* was recurrent in the teacher's diary: "They move more and better, search for free spaces in the field and how to score points fast" (TD, session nine). Finally, *autonomy* was another mentioned learning outcome. While at the beginning the students were totally dependant on the teacher, little by little, they began to organize themselves without arguing:

At the beginning of the class, I set this challenge: students had to lead the entire class without my help. I only gave them a piece of paper with today's matches, so they had to organize everything, distribute the roles... it demanded high commitment to avoid arguments. The

result was fabulous. The length of the learning unit generates automatisms that improves students' autonomy significantly (TD, session 11).

Self-construction. Many students positively commented the idea of self-construct things like t-shirts, trophies and medals: "I enjoyed so much building my own flag and trophy because I improved my artistic skills" (Javier, SOEQ), "I loved the idea of uniforms because I personally like crafts and I find it very nice to design our own shirt and have our own flag" (Carla, SOEQ). Some pupils reflected that the trophies and medals helped to reuse materials: "Each team won a self-constructed trophy made by ourselves and there were very nice things from ceramic to reusable things (plastic bottles, etc.) (Marcos, DG). The teacher also commented on the self-construction:

Today was the deadline to bring the self-constructed medal and trophies and it has been a successful proposal. There have been impressive handicrafts and some teams brought two instead of one trophy. They are highly motivated and this medals and trophies are a true reflection of it (TD, session 12).

Unfortunately, not all students' comments were positive, as some students created a nice medal and received a poor one:

"with respect to build medals and trophies ourselves, it has positive and negative sides. The positive is that it has been funny and it helped us improve our creativity. The negative is that not all students put the same effort to build them... big differences in the final result... so the final distribution wasn't fair" (Aurora, DG).

Several students provided a solution to this problem: "I would crowd the best medals in one group and the worsts in other group, and give the best to students who tried hard to build the medals" (Lucia, DG). Nevertheless, creating self-constructed materials was positive to build links between families: "I liked so much creating trophies... Nuria's mother got in touch with other mothers and we tried to meet. In the end, we could not meet but we tried and this is not usual. It had been a fantastic idea..." (Naiara, DG). However, not only among families, but also among family members: "we made together the medal for the end of the competition and he [son] considered that it was a good choice, although he could receive a different one that he like less" (Claudia, POEQ). Finally, the teacher also highlighted that the self-constructed materials were fundamental in the awards ceremony to increase students' motivation: "Today has been the official awards ceremony and all students have received a self-made medal and a certificate of participation... they were really happy" (TD, session 16).

Competitiveness. It was the only "negative" category/theme. Many students highlighted that this experience had increased excessively their competitiveness, leading them

to have arguments: “I think that in our class we are too competitive because when other teams scored a point, the opponent began to complain and look for some way to cancel the score” (Marco, DG). The teacher also saw that competitiveness was very high, especially during the culminating event:

“as a negative element, competitiveness has been too high during the finals, which forces me to use the following classes to promote personal values, because many students found difficult to accept the defeat or even admit that the other team had made a goal” (TD, session 14).

The score system could be considered of the leading causes of the competitiveness, but some saw positive elements: “with points, there is more competitiveness and that is good because we are motivated, but at the same time there are many problems” (Carla, DG). These points were especially significant during the finals: “the matches during recess [finals] were fantastic, but it would have been better to compete with no points or give points only for participation and fair play” (Lorena, SOEQ). It seemed that the score system led students to think that only the result was important: “in my team what really mattered was the result and I didn't realize that have fun and be with my friends playing during recess was more important” (Miguel, SOEQ). Finally, one teacher note reported how the instructor faced this competitiveness:

“when I began to see too much competitiveness, I started to increase the reflection time at the end of the classes. This was fundamental to lead students' competitiveness to a more positive side. I really wanted to increase students' fair play” (TD, session 10).

Discussion

The goal of the present study was to examine teacher, students and parents' perceptions of a Quidditch-Muggle Sport Education learning unit in Primary Education. From the analysis of all the data obtained, five positive categories/themes emerged; four positive: *enjoyment*, *novelty*, *learning and self-construction* and one negative: *competitiveness*.

The strongest category/theme was *enjoyment* and it was mentioned by all the participants: students, parents and teacher. It could be considered a recurrent outcome in the SEM. Cuevas et al., (2016), Strikwerda-Brown and Taggart (2001), and Wallhead and Ntoumanis (2004) found the same theme in their studies, conducted using different contents and in different contexts. Therefore, students seem to enjoy the PE class when it is organized using the SEM framework, regardless of the content used or the students' social background. Moreover, social recognition and social affiliation (social bonds) were found to be robust

contributors to students' perceived enjoyment of the PE class (Wallhead et al., 2013). Both are important elements of the model.

The first research question was: is "content novelty" enough to produce positive outcomes? Results indicated that both the content and the framework were considered novel and should be responsible for the outcomes. This was the first time that this group of students experienced the SEM and its framework (i.e., seasons, teams, competition, roles, final event...) and the game of Quidditch-Muggle and its background (Harry Potter), and both appeared in the students, parents and teacher's responses. They all acknowledged that the structured, round-robin, *formal competition* and the *culminating event* were very positive. The fact that the latter was conducted during recess, where younger students watched the oldest ones, was a complete success, because they felt like being in a real competition: in "little league" competitions, where siblings make the audience, "The quality of play differs dramatically...., but in all cases a note of festivity surrounds the competition" (Siedentop et al., 2011, p. 141). The length of the intervention program, creating a *season*, was another positive element, and the students did not feel tired; on the contrary, teacher's perceptions indicated that they continued highly motivated towards the end of the unit. The countries parade also contributed to the festive atmosphere and to the students' *affiliation* to their teams. Regarding the content, the Harry Potter theme offered many possibilities, even out of the class, since it encouraged reading among students. Therefore, both content and context novelty could be considered responsible of the experience's success. This idea connects with the SDT, since the satisfaction of the need for novelty increases students' intrinsic motivation, promoting adherence to PE practice (González-Cutre et al., 2016).

Learning emerged as another category/theme, and teamwork appeared as a learning outcome. One of the distinctive features of SE is that students are placed in heterogeneous groups from the first to the last session of the unit. Therefore, they are forced to work as a group, and teamwork seems a possible end-product of this context. Moreover, the use of roles is another distinguishing element of the model and it probably helped develop teamwork too, because each team member had to fulfil a role. Finally, formal competition and record keeping are also distinctive components of the SEM. Students probably pushed to work as a team and try to do their best to achieve the best final classification. Motor learning (competence) and autonomy were also mentioned as learning outcomes observed by the teacher. Previous studies also showed that the SEM can promote students' learning: game performance, competence (Fernández-Río et al. 2017; Layne & Hastie, 2004; MacPhail & Kinchin, 2004).

The successful use of self-made materials in PE under different names (i.e., inexpensive and innovative, improvised, low-cost or inexpensive, found, non-traditional, homemade) has been around for many decades (Fernández-Río & Méndez-Giménez, 2012). In the present study, *self-construction* was also present (i.e., trophies, medals), and it showed in teacher, parents and students' comments. To our knowledge, only two studies have previously used self-made materials in a SEM framework (Fernández-Río et al., 2013; Méndez-Giménez et al., 2015) and both produced positive outcomes. Therefore, this type of resources fit the model's framework and are positively appreciated by teachers, students and parents.

The second research question was: has there been an impact "at home"? Parents' comments showed that there was. Siendetop wanted the SEM to have an impact in the participants' life (Siedentop et al., 2019). Unfortunately, few studies have involved parents in a SEM season (participating) and/or study (assessing their perceptions). Until date, the majority of studies that have analysed perceptions after a SEM implementation have focused on the teacher and/or the students, but not on the parents (Martínez et al., 2016; Fernández-Río & Menéndez, 2017). To our knowledge, only two studies assessed this connection. Fernández-Río and Bernabé-Martín (2018) researched the connections between the SEM and parents in an AcroGymnastics season that used Facebook to promote parental involvement. Results showed that this combination produced a notable effect on parental involvement and changed positively their views on PE. Results from the present study are in line with this last finding. Harry Potter and the key elements of the SEM promoted students' interest and enthusiasm in PE, sharing it with their parents at home. Fernández-Río and Menéndez (2017) assess the impact of an innovative content (contactless kickboxing) and a hybridization of the SEM and Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility in students' with disabilities. Results from the mother of one girl with Down Syndrome revealed that both the experience helped to increase girl's responsibility at home (making homework on time, be more talkative with the family, helping with home duties...). Likewise, in this research, the innovative experience also helped students to work harder at home, especially in order to create self-constructed materials. Therefore, innovative contents as quidditch or contactless kickboxing may produce a positive impact at home.

The third and final research question was: is "competitiveness" an issue in the SEM? and results showed that it certainly is. Overemphasis on competition, results and scoreboards could be considered the "dark side" of the SEM (Fernández-Río & Casey, 2020). In the present study, both the students and the teacher highlighted that there was a problem with the scoreboard and the standings, which caused excessive competitiveness. It was considered a

motivator for some students, while others, fortunately, realized that it made them forget the most important goal of the model: have fun while practicing a sport with their peers (Siedentop et al., 2011). Formal competition is one of the pillars of the SEM, but Curnow and Macdonald (1995) warned against the emphasis on competition, because it could lead to, among other things, unequal participation. García-López and Gutiérrez (2015) found negative behaviours and excessive competitiveness among the students during a SE learning unit (arguments, verbal aggression, etc.). Excessive keenness on games and matches, as well as overemphasis on scoreboards and standings, can lead to negative competitiveness and a negative impact in students' development (Fernandez-Rio & Casey, 2020). Balance this pressure could be one of the reasons that have led researchers to promote the combination or hybridization of the SEM with other pedagogical models like Cooperative Learning or Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility: "Maybe this is what Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility adds to Sport Education: healthy competitiveness" (Fernandez-Rio & Menendez-Santurio, 2017, p. 193). This is an enriching way to strengthen the potential that each pedagogical model has and help students focus on personal and social values that are fundamental: respect the opponent, cooperate, etc. According to the SDT, excessive competitiveness can promote students' extrinsic motivation and create an ego-involving motivational climate. These outcomes would be negative for teachers, students and parents: anxiety, depressive symptoms, negative classroom environments (Ryan & Deci, 2002).

The present study is not without limitations. First, class size could be considered small, since there were only 17 students per class on average. Smaller classes are easier to teach, since there is more space and resources available. Second, individual interviews were not conducted with students or parents. They could have provided a better insight of the whole experience.

In conclusion, quidditch-muggle introduced through the SEM is a sport that may produce very positive outcomes: motivation, enjoyment, teamwork, improvement of family relationships, etc. The magical world of Harry Potter is an interesting topic that most students have considered innovative and creative. In that sense, as many research have revealed, there is no doubt that to create innovative settings in physical education classes is a key principle to make this curricular field more attractive and enjoyable.

References

Bessa, C., Hastie, P., Araújo, R., & Mesquita, I. (2019). What do we know about the development of personal and social skills within the sport Education Model: a Systematic Review. *Journal of Sports, Science, and Medicine*, 18, 812-829.

- Buchanan, A. M., & Barrow, B. (2016). The Table Tennis Triathlon: An Integrated Sport Education Season. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 87(1), 25-31, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2015.1109490>
- Bunker, D., & Thorpe, R. (1982). A model for the teaching of games in secondary schools. *Bulletin of Physical Education*, 18(1), 5-8.
- Calderón, A., Hastie, P. A., & Martínez de Ojeda, D. (2011). Sport Education Model: Physical Education for the new millenium? *Revista Española de Educación Física y Deportes*, 395, 63-79.
- Casey, A. (2014). Models-based practice: great white hope or white elephant? *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 19(1), 18-34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2012.726977>
- Casey, A. (2016). Models-Based Practice. In C.D. Ennis (ed.). *Handbook of Physical Education Pedagogy* (chapter 6). London: Routledge.
- Chen, Y. J., Sinelnikov, O. A., & Hastie, P. A. (2013). Professional development in physical education: introducing the sport education model to teachers in Taiwan. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Health, Sport and Physical Education*, 4(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18377122.2013.760424>
- Chong, S., & Penney, D. (2013). Promoting social and emotional learning outcomes in physical education: insights from a school-based research project in Singapore. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Health, Sport and Physical Education*, 4(3), 267-286. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18377122.2013.836768>
- Cohen, A., & Peachey, J. W. (2015). Quidditch: impacting and benefiting participants in a non-fictional manner. *Journal of Sport and Social Issues*, 39(6), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193723514561549>
- Cohen, A., Brown, B., & Peachey, J. W. (2012). The intersection of pop culture and non-traditional sports: an examination of the niche market of quidditch. *International Journal of Sport Management and Marketing*, 12(3/4), 180-197.
- Cohen, A., Melton, E., & Peachey, J. W. (2014). Investigating a coed sport's ability to encourage inclusion and equality. *Journal of Sport Management*, 28, 220-235. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019372351456154910.1123/jsm.2013-0329>
- Cuevas, R., García-López, L. M., & Contreras, O. (2015). Influence of the Sport Education Model in the psychological basic needs. *Cuadernos de Psicología del Deporte*, 15(2), 155-162, 2015.

- Curnow, J., & Macdonald, D. (1995). Can Sport Education be gender inclusive: A case study in an upper primary school. *ACHPER Healthy Lifestyles Journal*, *42*, 9-11.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). The general causality orientations scale: Self-determination in personality. *Journal of Research in Personality*, *19*, 109-134.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). *Handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607927>
- Evangelio, C., Sierra-Díaz, J., González-Víllora, S., & Fernández-Río, J. (2018). The sport education model in elementary and secondary education: a systematic review. *Movimiento*, *24*(3), 931-946. <https://doi.org/10.22456/1982-8918.81689>
- Farias, C., Valério, C., & Mesquita, I. (2018). Sport Education as a curriculum approach to student learning of invasion games: effects on game performance and game involvement. *Journal of Sports Sciences and Medicine*, *17*, 56-65.
- Farias, C., Harvey, S., Hastie, P. A., & Mesquita, I. (2019). Effects of situational constraints on students' game-play development over three consecutive Sport Education seasons of invasion games. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, *24*(3), 267-286. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2019.1571184>
- Farias, C., Mesquita, I., & Hastie, P. A. (2019). Student game-play performance in invasion games following three consecutive hybrid Sport Education seasons. *European Physical Education Review*, *25*(3), 691-712. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X18769220>
- Fernandez-Rio, J., & Mendez-Gimenez, A. (2012). Innovative practice through the use of self-made materials. In B. Dyson and A. Casey (eds.) *Cooperative learning in physical education* (pp. 42-56). Routledge.
- Fernández-Río, J., & Menéndez-Santurio, J. I. (2017). Teachers and students' perceptions of a hybrid Sport Education and Teaching for Personal and Social Responsibility learning unit. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, *36*(2), 185-196.
- Fernández-Río, J., & Casey, A. (2020). Sport Education as cooperative learning endeavour. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2020.1810220>
- Fernández-Río, J., Méndez-Giménez, A., & Méndez-Alonso, D. (2013). Effects of the three instructional approaches in adolescents' physical self-concept. *Cultura y Educación*, *25*(4), 509-521.
- Fittipaldi-Wert, J., S. J. Brock, P. A. Hastie, J. B. Arnold, & A. Guarino (2009). Effects of a sport Education curriculum model on the experiences of students with visual impairments. *Palaestra* *24*(3), 6-10.

- García-López, L. M., & Gutierrez, D. (2015). The effects of a sport education season on empathy and assertiveness. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 20(1), 1–16.
- Gonzalez-Cutre, D., & Sicilia, A. (2019). The importance of novelty satisfaction for multiple positive outcomes in physical education. *European Physical Education Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X18783980>
- Gonzalez-Cutre, D., Sicilia, A., Sierra, A. C., Ferriz, R., & Hagger, M. S. (2016). Understanding the need for novelty from the perspective of self-determination theory. *Personality and Individual Differences* 102, 159-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.06.036>
- Gonzalez-Cutre, D., Sicilia, A., Sierra, A. C., Ferriz, R., & Hagger, M. (2016). Understanding the need for novelty from the perspective of self-determination theory. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 102, 159-169
- Gray, S., Sproule, J., & Morgan, K. (2009). Teaching team invasion games and motivational climate. *European Physical Education Review*, 15(1), 65-89. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X09105212>
- Haerens, L., Kirk, D., Cardon, G. & De Bourdeaudhuij, I. (2011). Toward the development of a pedagogical model for health-based physical education. *Quest*, 63(3), 321–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2011.10483684>
- Hastie, P. A., & Wallhead, T. (2016). Models-based practice in physical education: The case for sport education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 35(4), 390–399. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2016-0092>
- Hastie, P. A., Martínez de Ojeda, D., & Calderón, A. (2011). A review of research on Sport Education: 2004 to the present. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 16(2). 103-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2010.53520>
- Hastie, P. A., & Casey, A. (2014). Fidelity in models-based practice research in sport pedagogy: A guide for future investigations. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 33(3), 422–431. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2013-0141>
- Hastie, P. A., Buchanan, A. M., Wadsworth, D. D., & Sluder, B. J. (2009) The Impact of an Obstacle Course Sport Education Season on Students' Aerobic Fitness Levels. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 80(4), 788-791.
- Hellison, D. (2001). Teaching responsibility through physical activity (2nd ed.). Human Kinetics.
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T. & Holubec, E. J. (2013). *Cooperation in the Classroom* (9th ed.). Interaction Book Company.

- Kao, C. (2019). Development of Team Cohesion and Sustained Collaboration Skills with the Sport Education Model. *Sustainability*, 11(8), 2348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082348>
- Libarkin, J. C., & Kurdziel, J. P. (2002). Research methodologies in science education: the qualitative-quantitative debate. *Journal of Geoscience Education*, 50(1), 78- 86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10899995.2002.12028053>
- Lugueti, C., Goodyear, V. A., & André, M. (2019). That is like a 24 hours-day tournament!': using social media to further an authentic sport experience within sport education. *Sport, Education and Society*, 24(1), 78-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2017.1292235>
- MacPhail, A., & Kinchin, G. (2004). The use of drawings as an evaluative tool: Students' experiences of sport education. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 9(1), 87-108.
- Méndez-Giménez, A.; Fernández-Río, J. y Méndez-Alonso, D. (2015). Sport Education Model versus traditional model: effects on motivation and sportsmanship. *Revista Internacional de Medicina y Ciencias de la Actividad Física y el Deporte*, 15(59), 449-466.
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2013). *Qualitative data analysis*. Sage.
- Montero, I., & Leon, O. G. (2007). A guide for naming research studies in psychology. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology*, 7, 847-862.
- Ntoumanis, N. (2001). A Self-Determination Approach to the Understanding of Motivation in Physical Education. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71(2), 225–242.
- Rinehart, R. (2000). Emerging/arriving sport: alternatives to formal sports. In J. Coakley & E. Dunning (Eds.), *Handbook of sports studies* (pp. 504-519). Sage
- Rocamora, I., González-Víllora, S., Fernández-Río, J., & Arias-Palencia, N. (2019). Physical activity levels, game performance and friendship goals using two different pedagogical models: Sport Education and Direct Instruction. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 24(1), 87-102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2018.1561839>
- Rovegno, I. (2006). Situated perspectives on learning. In D. Kirk, M. O' Sullivan, & D. MacDonald (Eds.), *Handbook of physical Education*. Sage.
- Rowling, J. K. (1997). *Harry Potter and the philosopher's stone*. Bloomsbury.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2002). An overview of self-determination theory: An orga-nismic dialectical perspective. En E. L. Deci y R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *Handbook of Self-Determination research* (pp. 3–33). The University of Roches-ter Press.
- Ryan, R. M. & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Publications.
- Siedentop, D., Hastie, P., & van der Mars, H. (2019). *Complete guide to sport education*. Human Kinetics.

- Strikwerda-Brown, J. & Taggart, A. (2001). No longer voiceless and exhausted: sport education and the primary generalist. *Australian Council for Health, Physical Education, and Recreation Healthy Lifestyles Journal*, 48(4), 14–17.
- Wahl-Alexander, Z., Hastie, P. A., & Johnson, N. (2018). Using a Fishing Sport Education Season to Promote Outside Engagement. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 89(7), 28-33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2018.1490222>
- Wallhead, T. L. Garn, A. C., & Vidoni, C. (2013). Sport Education and social goals in physical education: relationships with enjoyment, relatedness, and leisure-time physical activity. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 18(4), 427-441, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2012.690377>
- Wallhead, T. L., & Ntoumanis, N. (2004). Effects of a sport education intervention on students' motivational responses in physical education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 23, 4–18.
- Wallhead, T., & O'Sullivan, M. (2007). A didactic analysis of content development during peer teaching task of a Sport Education Season. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 12(3), 225-243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408980701610177>
- Ward, J. K., Hastie, P. A., Wadsworth, D. D., Foote, S., Brock, S. J., & Hollett, N. (2017). A Sport Education fitness season's impact on students' fitness levels, knowledge, and in-class physical activity. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 88(3), 346-351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2017.1321100>